

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: ITALY

LimnoConsulting

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LimnoConsulting is a one-woman environmental research and consulting business founded in 2012. I am LimnoConsulting's founder and sole proprietor, and I hold a PhD from Kent State University (Ohio, USA).

LimnoConsulting's mission is to provide diagnostics and solutions in basic (research) and applied limnology (research and consulting), with a focus on environmentally friendly, science-based, "green" solutions to limnological and other environmental problems.

Fig. 1 Experimenting with macrophytes and snails.

Projects involve ad hoc collaborations with other researchers or consultants from all over Europe and beyond, thus allowing LimnoConsulting to participate in a wide spectrum of projects, from small to large.

Given the poor attention to limnology in Italy, much of LimnoConsulting's recent projects have focused mainly on research. Research includes field and laboratory surveys and manipulative experiments. Basic ecological projects aim at providing knowledge that could be useful in solving real-life problems.

LimnoConsulting's and my core expertise is in benthic and shallow freshwater ecosystems, especially in macrophyte-based ecological communities and the application of their ecology to provide a solution to problems such as high-water turbidity or low biodiversity (e.g., due to eutrophication). Much of LimnoConsulting's research and consulting revolves around the concept of the "alternate stable states" theory for shallow lakes, according to which a healthy submerged vegetation community can at least mitigate the negative effects of eutrophication or siltation. To this end, a healthy macrophyte-dwelling invertebrate community is needed to attain or maintain the desirable clear-water stable state.

Macrophyte-based research has involved close collaborations with The Norsk Institutt for Vannforskning (NIVA) and has mainly focused on field surveys (Mjelde *et al.* 2012). Recent investigations on benthic invertebrates have been carried out mostly in collaboration with researchers at the University of L'Aquila. Other projects deal with macrophyte-invertebrate interactions (Gross & Lombardo 2018) (Fig. 1), environmental indices (Miccoli *et al.* 2013; Lombardo & Mjelde 2014), catchment-scale surveys (Lombardo 2005). Current research projects (as yet unpublished) investigate the potential for

Fig. 2 Macroinvertebrate sampling on shoreline moss.

shoreline moss to increase local benthic biodiversity (Fig. 2), and the ability of aquatic gastropods (possibly keystone players in macrophyte-based ecological communities) to withstand short-term exposure to air. More information and my complete publication history are available at the [LimnoConsulting website](#) and my [ResearchGate profile](#).

Experience as a consultant has come mainly from international projects, especially in the United States (aquatic vegetation assessments and diagnostic/feasibility studies) and in Norway; the latter including projects for the European Union (expert testimony within the context of the EU's Nitrates Directive). I have also taught environmental biology and limnology and I have served as an external advisor for two student Theses as an adjunct professor at the University of L'Aquila.

I have founded LimnoConsulting to have the freedom to pursue my own scientific and professional interests while cultivating my love of teaching. The one-person business has been a necessity to have a firm as much bureaucracy-free as possible, but my publication history is witness of my love for team playing. The main obstacle that I have encountered ever since coming back to my homeland of Italy is the paucity of consulting projects in my country, but I keep myself quite busy with limnological research and international projects. My professional experience has taught me to have a broad spectrum of expertise to diversify project participation, while keeping the focus on a relatively narrow ecological topic to be able to produce publication-level research and consultancy.

References

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